

Sorption of tetracycline in montmorillonite suspensions

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Abstract : Adsorption of widely used antibiotic tetracycline under various conditions of pH, temperature, ionic strength and exchangeable cations on montmorillonite was examined. Maximum adsorption occurs at pH 3 which is near pK_a value of tetracycline. The shapes of isotherms depended on the nature of exchangeable cations. The adsorption varied directly with the polarizing power of the exchangeable cation and inversely with changes in temperature, ionic strength and with the added humic substances. The enthalpy changes (ΔH°) calculated from the temperature coefficient of the equilibrium constant, showed that process is exothermic. The adsorption of tetracycline on montmorillonite gives rise to an entropy loss. Various studies i.e. IR, X-ray, Freundlich adsorption isotherms revealed the existence of protonation or coordination (or both) between exchangeable cation of clay and $>C=O$ group of the tetracycline besides physical adsorption. In presence of field sewage effluent the adsorption of tetracycline increased which might be due to cation bridging in between tetracycline and montmorillonite clay.

Keywords : Tetracycline, adsorption, montmorillonite, ionic strength, humic substance.

Introduction

The use of antibiotics as veterinary pharmaceuticals has now become an integral part of the animal food industry because of their valuable contributions towards the treatment of various diseases¹, as growth promoters² and in improving feed efficiency³. The tetracycline is a broad spectrum antibiotic widely used in animal production. Tetracyclines contribute approximately 50% of total antibiotics production. After the application to animals, antibiotics will eventually enter the environment and the major route of entering the environment is the excretion of faeces and urine from medicated animals in live stocks and poultry farms and the subsequent application of contaminated manure as fertilizer in the agricultural land. Thus there is a genuine concern that residual concentration of antibiotics in agricultural soils may reach easily to the level of pesticides if the manure loading for fertilizer increased to kg level per hectare⁴. The adsorption and retention of antibiotics have been shown to be influenced by pH⁵, organic matter⁶, clay content, and to a lesser degree by the concentrations of ions present in the solution⁷, temperature and type of exchangeable cations⁸ present on the clay.

The purpose of this study was to determine the influ-

ence of pH, temperature, solution ionic strength, exchangeable cations and humic substance on the nature of the adsorption of widely used veterinary pharmaceutical tetracycline (TC) on Akli bentonite clay using batch experiment.

Results and discussion

The influence of pH on the adsorption of tetracycline on all the studied samples (Fig. 1) indicated a strong correlation between pH and adsorption, the maximum adsorption was observed at pH 3 and thereafter a decrease in adsorption with the increase in pH. As expected,

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on tetracycline adsorption by montmorillonites.

maximum adsorption occurs at a pH value near the pK_{a1} value (3.3). As the tetracycline molecules can undergo protonation-deprotonation reactions and adopt different ionic species depending on the pH of solution, the maximum adsorption at pH 3 may be attributed to the cationic exchange interactions that are dominant at lower pH values when tetracycline is positively charged⁹.

The data showing the effect of solution ionic strength on sorption of tetracycline (Table 1) indicated that adsorption of tetracycline decreases with the increase in the ionic strength of the solute. The adsorption as affected more where the saturating cation is Al^{3+} or Fe^{3+} rather than Na^+ or K^+ . The decrease in the adsorption with increasing ionic strength (0.0–0.09) ranged from 23 to 30.2% (Table 1). Decreasing adsorption with increasing ionic strength may be due to (i) competition of tetracycline with increasing amount of cations for sites¹⁰, (ii) formation of non adsorbable metal-tetracycline complex in solution¹¹.

Table 1. Adsorption of tetracycline on montmorillonites saturated with different cations at several ionic strengths (of appropriate salt) at 298 K

Ionic strength (I)	Amount of tetracycline adsorbed g^{-1} clay			
	Al-mont.	Fe-mont.	Na-mont.	K-mont.
0.000	2200	2120	1860	1820
0.009	2090	2030	1780	1750
0.018	1960	1910	1690	1645
0.036	1855	1816	1605	1575
0.054	1760	1725	1530	1500
0.072	1640	1605	1460	1445
0.09	1536	1500	1410	1395

The Freundlich relationship can be used to describe the tetracycline sorption results on montmorillonite ($R^2 > 0.98$). The linear form of this equation is : $\log C_s = \log K_f + 1/n \log C_e$, where C_s (mg/kg) is the amount of tetracycline adsorbed by soil, C_e ($mg L^{-1}$) is the equilibrium concentration of tetracycline in solution and K_f and $1/n$ are constants. K_f is the amount adsorbed for a unit equilibrium concentration of tetracycline, and $1/n$ is a measure of intensity of adsorption reflecting the degree of linearity of adsorption. The values are given in Table 2. The values of $1/n$ during tetracycline adsorption on Al- and Fe-saturated montmorillonites were more than unity, indicating an S type of isotherm (Fig. 2). The val-

Table 2. Freundlich adsorption isotherm constants of tetracycline adsorption at 298 and 313 on montmorillonites saturated with different cations

Sorbent	Tetracycline					
	298 K			313 K		
	K_f	$1/n$	r^2	K_f	$1/n$	r^2
Al-montmorillonite	365	1.210	0.97	328	1.110	0.99
Fe-montmorillonite	314	1.165	0.96	282	1.105	0.98
Na-montmorillonite	248	0.710	0.98	216	0.695	0.97
K-montmorillonite	238	0.695	0.98	205	0.675	0.96

ues indicated that new sites became available to the solute as the adsorption occurred, whereas values of the $1/n$ for Na- and K-montmorillonites were less than unity indicating an L type of isotherms^{12,13}. The 'L' type of isotherms may arise because of minimum competition of solvent for sites on the adsorbing surface. The slope of

Fig. 2(a). Adsorption isotherms of tetracycline adsorption on montmorillonites.

Fig. 2(b). Adsorption isotherms of tetracycline adsorption on montmorillonites.

the isotherm decreases steadily with the increase in solute concentration, because vacant sites become less accessible with the progressive covering of the surface. The curvilinear isotherm suggests that the number of available sites for the sorption become a limiting factor.

Adsorption of tetracycline was in the order : Al-clay > Fe-clay > Na-clay > K-clay. It indicates that the adsorption decreases as the polarizing power of exchangeable cation decreases. Higher adsorption during Al- and Fe-clay suspension may be attributed to its polarizing ability by increasing the acidity of inner-layer water. An increase in temperature from 298 to 313 K results in the decrease of adsorption (Fig. 2). A decrease in the adsorption with temperature may be attributed to the change in the energy of adsorption or weakening (or both) of the van der Waals forces of attraction between tetracycline and clay surface, causing a decrease in physical adsorption.

Adsorption of tetracycline by clay suspension increased in the presence of field waste water effluent (FEW) (Fig. 3). It appears that the structural suitability of tetracycline for surface complexation allowed for binding to montmorillonite and resulted in a higher extent of adsorption. This may be due to formation of a metal bridge in between carboxylic residue of tetracycline molecule and negatively charged clay as :

In presence of humic substances (HS) (Fig. 3) the adsorption of tetracycline on Al-, Fe-, Na- and K-montmorillonites decreased. The decrease in adsorption might be due to blocking of the access of tetracycline molecule to the clay interlayer sorption sites by HS¹⁴.

X-Ray diffraction analysis indicated expansion of 0.16 to 0.38 nm in the basal thickness on complexing of different cation montmorillonites for the tetracycline. The expansion was more for metal-clay sorption than metal-clay-HS sorption. From these data it may be concluded

Fig. 3(a). Adsorption isotherms of tetracycline adsorption on montmorillonites in presence of HS and field effluent sewage.

Fig. 3(b). Adsorption isotherms of tetracycline adsorption on montmorillonites in presence of HS and field effluent sewage.

that the studied antibiotic tetracycline was sorbed in the interlayer of montmorillonite while in presence of humic substances the adsorption of tetracycline occurs in the interlayer's of the clay-humic substances complex via cation bridging as :

Further the dissociation of water molecules in contact with exchangeable cations bring about protonation, the degree of hydrolysis depends upon the polarizing power of the cations¹⁵.

The protons released bind the antibiotics molecule to the clay surface by ionic bonding as :

Desorption studies denoted that besides chemisorptions some physical adsorption of the studied antibiotic tetracycline may also occur. The physical adsorption may occur through formation of hydrogen bonds between the protonated species on the mineral surface and the antibiotic species at crystal edge and basal surface of clay as :

The above conclusions are also supported by thermodynamic parameters viz. standard free energy change (ΔG°), enthalpy change (ΔH°) and entropy changes (ΔS°) with the thermodynamic equilibrium constant (K_0) calculated by the Biggar and Cheung¹⁶ method from the adsorption curves. The values are given in Table 3.

The values of K_0 (Table 3) are found more than unity i.e. tetracycline has a higher preference for montmorillonite surface, and decrease in the order : Al- > Fe- > Na- > K-montmorillonites, confirming our earlier deductions regarding the order of adsorption. The values of K_0 also show a decrease with the increase in the temperature. The values of ΔG° are negative and increase with a rise in temperature, pointing towards the spontaneity of a reaction with a greater affinity of montmorillonite for tetracycline. The values of ΔG° show that for tetracycline the driving forces of the reaction, the strength of adsorption, and the degree of order attained during the adsorption reaction are : Al- > Fe- > Na- > K-montmorillonites. The negative values of overall adsorption heat (ΔH°) indicate the exothermic nature of reaction with a strong binding of tetracycline molecules on clay surface. The values of ΔH° also show that the adsorption occurs through covalent bonding mechanisms. The values of entropy change (ΔS°) during the interactions of tetracycline on montmorillonite are negative, indicating that clay-tetracycline complexes are stable. Association, fixation or immobilization of the antibiotics molecule as a

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters for tetracycline adsorption at 298 and 313 montmorillonites saturated with different cations

Sorbent	K_0		ΔG° (kJ/mol)		ΔH°	ΔS°
	298 K	313 K	298 K	313 K	(kJ/mol)	(J/mol K)
Al-montmorillonite	478	343	-15.32	-15.20	-17.15	-6.1
Fe-montmorillonite	442	315	-15.09	-14.97	-17.51	-8.1
Na-montmorillonite	401	294	-14.86	-14.79	-15.95	-3.6
K-montmorillonite	368	270	-14.65	-14.57	-15.26	-2.1

result of adsorption, resulted in a loss of the degrees of freedom of the antibiotics molecule, producing negative entropy effects¹⁷. All these mechanisms were also supported by FTIR spectra. A shift of bands at 1620 cm^{-1} ($\Delta\nu = -25$ to -15 cm^{-1}) and 1380 cm^{-1} ($\Delta\nu = +10$ to $+15\text{ cm}^{-1}$) attributed to a $>C=O$ stretching vibration and to C-N stretching of CONH_2 group respectively suggests that amide group played an important role during complexation of tetracycline with Na-, K-, Al- and Fe-montmorillonite and clay-HS complexes supporting the proposed mechanisms.

Conclusions :

The antibiotic tetracycline is more mobile (less adsorbed) in soil at high pH and high salt concentration (ionic strength), while in presence of field sewage effluents the accumulation of tetracycline was more. The adsorption of tetracycline also depends on the polarizing power of cations. The X-ray and IR data suggest protonation and/or coordination of metallic cations of clay to the $>C=O$ of amide group of tetracycline besides physical adsorption.

Experimental

Through treatment with 1 N NaCl , a $< 2\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ fraction of montmorillonite (bentonite sample from Akli in Rajasthan, India, member of the group beidellites) was purified by sedimentation and centrifugation and converted into Cl^- free Na-saturated clay. Homoionic suspensions of K-, Fe- and Al-montmorillonite were obtained from the Na form by the ion exchange technique. A natural humic substance [complex aromatic macromolecules with numerous acidic groups, polysaccharides, fatty acids and long aliphatic side chains (HS)] was extracted from the whole soil. The whole soil was saturated with Na^+ by washing several times with 1 M NaCl , 0.1 M NaOH . The sample was then agitated on a flat bed shaker at $150\text{ cycle's min}^{-1}$ for 24 h at temperature $298 \pm 2\text{ K}$. After

centrifugation for 10 min at 13000 rpm the supernatant was collected and adjusted to pH 7 with 0.01 M HCl . The supernatant was dialyzed with deionized water till free from excess salts. The concentration of suspensions varied from 8.6 to $10.0\text{ g per }100\text{ mL}$. The CEC of clay was $73\text{ C mol (p}^+) \text{ kg}^{-1}$ clay. The total surface area was 690, 680, 650 and m^2/g for Na-, K-, Fe- and Al-saturated montmorillonites respectively. The pH of soil humic substance was 3.5.

Adsorption experiments were conducted using 10 mL of the appropriate montmorillonite suspensions and humic substance separately in a large number of glass stoppered tubes, adding various amounts of standard tetracycline solution ($0\text{--}15\text{ mL of }20\text{ mg mL}^{-1}$), and making up the volume to 50 mL with distilled water. The suspensions were shaken for 40 h in a constant temperature water bath at $298 \pm 1\text{ K}$ and $313 \pm 1\text{ K}$ (preliminary studies indicated that equilibrium was attained in $< 33\text{ h}$) followed by centrifugation for 15 min at 13000 rpm. The supernatants were estimated using UV-Visible spectrophotometrically at two wavelengths 280 and 370 nm (preliminary studies showed that a linear response for the studied antibiotics was obtained in the range $0\text{--}25\text{ mg L}^{-1}$). The amount of tetracycline adsorbed was obtained from the amount added minus that remaining in the supernatants.

The effect of the equilibrium pH on adsorption was investigated at six pH values ranging between 2 and 11 obtained by adding 0.1 M HCl or 0.1 M NaOH as required. Ten mL of appropriate clay and 15 mL of tetracycline solution (20 mg mL^{-1}), and making up the volume to 50 mL with water. The suspensions were shaken for 40 h in a constant temperature water bath at $25 \pm 1\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The amount of tetracycline adsorbed was calculated as cited above. The influence of solution ionic strength was determined by equilibrating 15 mL of tetracycline solution ($20\text{ }\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$), which was initially prepared in appro-

appropriate solution of different electrolytes ranging from 0.00166 to 0.3 N with 10 mL of the appropriate clay suspension at constant volume of 50 mL and at 25 ± 1 °C. The amount of tetracycline adsorbed was calculated as cited above.

To study the influence of field waste water effluent (FEW) (COD 25 mg/L and EC 1.14 mS/cm) 10 mL of appropriate clay was shaken with 20 mL of FEW for 12 h to reach pre-equilibrium. After pre-equilibrium 15 mL of tetracycline solution (20 mg mL^{-1}) was added and the volume was made up to 50 mL with water. The suspensions were shaken for 40 h in a constant temperature water bath at 25 ± 1 °C. The amount of tetracycline adsorbed was calculated as cited above. Adsorption in presence of humic substance (HS) was investigated in another set of experiments by pre-equilibrating the appropriate clay solution with 1 g HS/L for 1 week. After pre-equilibration 10 mL of appropriate clay solution was shaken with 0–15 mL of 20 mg mL^{-1} tetracycline solution for 40 h at a constant volume of 50 mL in a constant temperature water bath at 25 ± 1 °C. The amount of tetracycline adsorbed was calculated as cited above. All the experiments were conducted in duplicate with suitable reagent and clay blanks. X-Ray and analyses of different cation saturated clays and their complexed samples were performed as discussed elsewhere.

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